

“UPSTREAM” IN SEVEN STEPS

Image: Skryje, Moravia, Czech Republic. Photo: Gavin Keeney.

EPIGRAPH

“But the love will have been enough; all those impulses of love return to the love that made them. Even memory is not necessary for love. There is a land of the living and a land of the dead and the bridge is love, the only survival, the only meaning.”

–Thornton Wilder, *The Bridge of San Luis Rey* (1927)

THE BRIDGE

This above-cited passage from the end of Wilder’s 1927 masterpiece is generally considered the authorial equivalent of all other forms of negating determinism (theological, nihilist, etc.), insofar as he places the figure of the bridge (an Incan rope bridge that collapsed at the very opening of his novel, killing five people) at the intersection of two worlds; a topological and tropological gesture that secretly conceals one world. In making the cause of the disaster (sought for in divine agency as retribution by the Franciscan monk who witnessed and catalogued the event and its possible purposes) impersonal agency bar none, or love itself, Wilder – through the pure vehicle of the novel – unveils a primary truth given to Art and to the production of worlds. The Franciscan monk searches for and misses the underlying common ground for the five deaths at this one moment, whereas the godlike author (having created the characters *and* the event) is able to dispassionately disclose, however slowly over the course of the narrative, that the common element in each distinct life was a response to the event of love, bringing them all together at the

decisive moment – each according to their own experience and their individual dramas. In a word, the drama is “immanence” (conjoined and fused to its Other, “transcendence”).

SEVEN STEPS

The following seven steps illustrate a methodology for converting the contemporary open-access (OA), peer-reviewed, online scholarly journal model to the Edition of One (EO1) “No Rights” model – i.e., a shift away from single-author or co-authored articles managed by academic gatekeepers to collectively produced, anonymously editioned works with little or no relation to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) law or academic fashions. “Upstream,” in this scenario, connotes the operative principles of the model. “Downstream” connotes the day-to-day operations of the endeavor. Both terms imply a “bridge” from which to observe “what” is upstream and “what” is downstream. Thus, the value of Thornton Wilder’s remarkable apperception of an ecological milieu that is also a semi-divine milieu. “Upstream” also signals Theo Angelopoulos’ extraordinary film, *The Weeping Meadow* (2004), where, indeed, “drops drip.”

1/ Drop peer review

Peer review has been proven to be gamed, especially *blind peer review*

2/ Establish a critical collegium for established and emerging scholars

This would constitute a de facto *scriptorium*

3/ Shift “Leftward” and “Upstream” while engaging with established and emerging scholars downstream

Removing peer review and *authorial privileges* demolishes egotistic and careerist agendas

4/ Collectively conceptualize, produce, and edition all articles

Renouncing *authorial presences* further demolishes egotistic and careerist agendas

5/ Publish anonymously and via “No Rights” status (CC0 OA license or beyond)

“Anonymous” is the only means to evade the *last vestiges of IPR law* otherwise known as moral rights

6/ Move to print journal status and “graduated OA” as transitional state

This permits the journal to *pay authors for their labor* and restores the ontic basis of publishing

7/ Share all proceeds amongst the collegium based on labor

This could be “managed” through *blockchain and cryptocurrency*

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“Edition of One,” *Medium* (October 18, 2023)

<https://medium.com/@agencecx/edition-of-one-5059f48380c4>

“Useless Collegia,” *Zenodo* (August 13, 2022)

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